

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-114- IG-10% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	89	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	lm 4 114
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/15/2022 16:52:06 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 20:12:29 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.105	1634255	49.97	188472
2	6.575	1635944	50.03	166861

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-113-IG-10% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221116
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 113
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/16/2022 12:01:17 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:21:39 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.123	275862	2.41	29808
2	6.572	11155985	97.59	1153105